

Soil and Crop management relation with water use efficiency in Dryland agriculture

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ABSTRACT

The problem of shortage of water to crops can be resolved by increasing total water supply available to plants, increasing water use relative to other losses and efficient management of scarce water. Biophysically, solutions to many of the problems will require the improvement of soil, water, and crop management at the field, plot, and farm level: first, to increase the capture and retention of incoming (rain) water; and second, to maximize the proportion of that water productively transpired by the crop. Dry land agriculture under rain fed conditions is found mainly in Africa, the Middle East, Asia, and Latin America. In the harsh environments of Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) and West Asia and North Africa (WANA), water is the principal factor limiting crop yield. A review has been carried out on soil and crop management research that can increase the water use efficiency. The WANA production systems are dominated by cereals, primarily wheat in the wetter and barley in the drier areas, in rotation with mainly food legumes such as chickpea, lentil and forage legumes. The SSA production systems are generally characterized by cereal/legume mixed-cropping dominated by maize, millet, sorghum, and wheat. The major constraints in both regions to crop production are low soil fertility, insecure rainfall, and low-productive genotypes, low adoption of improved soil and crop management practices, and lack of appropriate institutional support. Different cropping systems and accompanying technologies are discussed. Results indicate that there is an advantage to apply these technologies but being function of socio-economic and bio-physical conditions. It is recommended that future research focuses on integrated technology development while taking into account also different levels of scale such as field, village, and watershed.

KEYWORDS

Soil and Crop Management, Water Use Efficiency, Impact, Rain Fed, Technologies, West Asia, Africa

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Recent agricultural research has resulted in innovations which enable farmers to increase their yields. Mechanization of farm operations, proper and timely tillage and sowing, planting geometry, new crop varieties, use of fertilizers, pesticides, and herbicides in suitable crop rotations all contribute to the increase and stabilization of agricultural production. However, across wide tracts of Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) and West Asia and North Africa (WANA), water scarcity is a major factor limiting agricultural production for millions of resource-poor dry land farmers. The small total amount of rain combined with its erratic and

unreliable occurrence constrain the achievement of stable, sustainable production systems providing satisfactory, low-risk livelihoods. The occurrence of periods of water deficit for crop production, referred to as ‘climatic drought’, is commonly observed and leads to low water availability for crops. Besides climatic drought, crop water stress may also result from low levels of plant available water in the soil profile due either to the existence of physical barriers to water infiltration (e.g., surface sealing) or to soil chemical or physical limitations to plant root growth and root water uptake. Drought resulting from such factors will be referred to as ‘edaphic

drought' since it is caused by soil-specific conditions rather than by limited rainwater supply, and can occur even under conditions of sufficient and well-distributed rainfall. Finally, even where water is very scarce, particularly in the driest areas, a surprisingly small proportion of the available water is actually transpired by the crop. Non-productive losses include surface runoff, deep drainage, evaporation from the soil surface and deep cracks, and transpiration by weeds.

Within this context, innovations in soil and crop management are sought by agricultural scientists to make maximum use of the water available for crop growth. In general, in addition to soil fertility management, two main agronomic strategies have been identified to increase water use efficiency: soil and water management, and cropping system management. Countries of SSA and WANA the considerable variations in rainfall both within and between countries as well as the unequal distribution of rainfall throughout the year. This rainfall variability combined with large variations in other climatic factors as well as large differences in soil types, makes it hard for scientists to develop general "blue print" solutions, but rather necessitates the development of site-specific technologies to help the resource poor farmers of WANA and SSA.

This paper reviews the present status of research on cropping systems and crop complementarities in dry land agriculture in the light of increasing water-use efficiency (WUE). An example of a decision tree on how to optimize soil water use, and examples of impact of relevant techniques are presented. The paper focuses on representative countries of the WANA and SSA regions (*i.e.*, Egypt, Burkina Faso, Iran, Jordan, Kenya, Mali, Morocco, Niger, South Africa, Syria, Turkey, and Zimbabwe) that are members of the Optimizing Soil Water Use (OSWU) Consortium.

Definition of Water-Use Efficiency (WUE)

In its most general sense, WUE refers to the ratio of the amount of water used to achieve a given output. Both the 'type' of water whose use is being optimized (rainfall, (evapo) transpired water, irrigation water, etc. and the type of output vary according to the process that is being optimized and the objectives of the optimization process. WUE may therefore refer to crop yield per unit rainfall,

total biomass per unit irrigation water, or mass of hydrocarbons stored per unit water transpired, to cite but a few definitions. In addition, WUE can be defined at different spatial and temporal (daily, weekly, seasonal, yearly) scales.

Regarding spatial scales, it can be defined, for instance at:

(i) The watershed scale, as the ratio of the amount of biomass produced to the amount of water flowing into this watershed (precipitation) minus the amount of water flowing out [kg biomass per m³ water or kg per mm].

(ii) The farm scale, as the ratio of the economic value of the produce to the amount of water consumed by the crop (US\$ per m³ water).

(iii) The field scale, as the ratio of the amount of biomass produced (total dry matter, grain yield, tuber yield, etc.) to the amount of water evapotranspired (*i.e.*, transpiration by crop and evaporation from soil) [kg biomass per mm water evapotranspired].

(iv) The individual plant scale, as the ratio of the amount of biomass produced to the amount of water transpired by the plant (kg biomass per mm water transpired).

As a consequence, WUE should be replaced with more specific definitions such as precipitation-use efficiency (PUE), irrigation water-use efficiency (IWUE), transpiration efficiency (TE), etc., and the calculation procedures should be clearly explained. This is particularly important if WUE is not considered as yield over evapotranspiration.

Dry Land Agriculture and its Traditional Crop Production Systems

In both WANA and SSA, the crop production systems are integrated closely with livestock production (e.g., stubble grazing, manure supply). The main characteristics have the wide range of soil physical and chemical constraints for which solutions are required. Depending on the agro-ecological zone, crops are grown either as a mono-culture or as intercrop with a legume at low planting density. Intercropping enables spreading of risks over two contrasting crops and of labor peaks, and allows exploitation of the long rainy season during good years. Planting densities depend on the expected rainfall and the soil type. Because of crop establishment problems mainly due to prolonged dry spells repeated sowing is common. Generally,

weeding is done by hand, and external inputs such as fertilizers or pesticides are insufficiently applied or not at all.

For both regions, the importance of legumes for nutritious food and feed, their contribution to subsequent cereal productivity through biologically fixed N, for breaking disease and pest cycles, and conserving farming resources and promoting sustainable agriculture has been documented (Osman *et al.*, 1990, Bationo *et al.*, 1991, Harris *et al.*, 1991, Wiltshire and Du Preez, 1993, Muehlbauer and Keiser, 1994).

Soil degradation, in the form of soil erosion and loss of soil organic matter and essential nutrients, is an increasing problem in both regions. Legume cultivation to increase soil organic matter, to fix nitrogen and spare soil mineral N, to eliminate cereal diseases, and to provide more flexible weed-control options offers a means of alleviating soil degradation in the face of inevitable crop intensification in dry areas. The integration of legumes in the cropping systems can also reduce soil erosion substantially (Zougmore *et al.*, 1998).

Strategies to Optimize Water Use Efficiency

The basic principle of efficient water- use for plant production lies in optimizing each of the components of the soil water balance. There are two distinct management periods. The first is the period of rain storage lasting from harvesting of the previous crop till sowing of the next. Under semi-arid climatic conditions, the soil and water management strategies during this period should aim at maximizing soil water storage, i.e., at maximizing the gains and minimizing the losses in equation 1. The soil water balance during the period of rain storage can be written as follows:

$$\Delta S = P + I \pm D \pm R - E - T$$

where,

ΔS = change in the water content in the potential root zone

P = precipitation

I = irrigation

D = downward drainage out of the root zone (-) or upward capillary flow into the root zone (+)

R = runoff (-) or run on (+)

E = evaporation from the soil surface

T = transpiration

The growing season is the second management period, lasting from sowing till harvesting of the crop. The soil water balance can then be rearranged in the following form:

$$T = P + I \pm \Delta S \pm D \pm R - E \quad (2)$$

To allow for the maximum amount of water to be available for transpiration (T) and thereby leading to maximum plant production the parameters on the right hand side of equation 2 should be optimized.

Soil and Water Management

Efficient capture of rainwater by the soil requires that the infiltration rate equals the rainfall intensity for the entire duration of a storm. Otherwise the excess water ponds on the soil run off and are lost to the soil crop water economy at that place. The severity of runoff is a function of rainfall quantity and intensity, land slope, soil and surface characteristics, and plant cover. Of these only the last two are potentially subject to control on a routine basis, although land slopes can be modified by building terraces. Previous research has mainly concentrated on soil physical characteristics and how to ameliorate the limitations they impose on infiltration either directly by surface sealing (or crusting) or indirectly by slow subsurface percolation. Surface crusting and restricted infiltration are also widespread problems in dry areas and may limit tillage opportunities. Technologies affecting soil physical characteristics in order to increase water availability comprise mainly tillage and anti-erosion measures.

Tillage

Tillage operations (with their form, depth, frequency, and timing) and the management of crop residues are important in water conservation, particularly in dry areas. In rain fed agriculture in semi-arid regions, conventional tillage has mainly four purposes:

- (i) To prepare a seedbed
- (ii) To promote infiltration
- (iii) To conserve water within the soil profile
- (iv) To prevent wind and water erosion.

Where the land has been untilled since the previous harvest, in all but the lightest soils it is necessary to wait until the early rains have

cumulatively wetted the soil sufficiently to permit the entry of an implement. A particularly vicious circle can arise where the crusted surface of 'hard setting' soil resists infiltration and promotes the runoff of much of the heavy early-season rainfall. Research-derived recommendations to cultivate after harvest or before the next rains to assist infiltration are often inapplicable: one problem is the indigenous practice of in situ grazing of residues, another that the power available for tillage is inadequate to overcome the natural strength of the dry soil. For the driest environments, it may be advantageous to rethink the cropping pattern and its relation to the tillage requirements for water infiltration and weed control.

Currently, most staple cereals continue extracting soil water beyond the end of the rainy season, so that after harvest many soils are unworkable until the next season. One solution is to give priority to the basic needs of the tillage operation (rather than those of a particular crop) and to increase the flexibility of the cropping system by introducing new varieties and species of shorter growth cycle (Jones, 1987). The underlying logic in all cases should be soil management to optimize the provision of water to crops most able to utilize it productively. Increasing the surface area of soil exposed to radiation and wind by deep plowing increases the loss of water through evaporation. Maintenance of the soil structure is the basic requirement for any package aimed at recuperating and maintaining the productivity of soil.

Conventional or clean tillage has a long traditional and historical basis in rain fed cropping areas of the world. However, conservation tillage, which requires that stubble residues remain on or near the soil surface, is becoming more widely used. The no tillage system is a powerful point of entry to solve the problems of soil erosion, soil fertility, and soils with low water holding capacity (Lal, 1976). Crop yields from no tillage agriculture are usually as high as or higher than yields produced by conventional tillage (Campbell *et al.*, 1984). However, no-till systems create other challenges that need to be coped with, such as weed and pest infestations. Tillage research in semi-arid Southern Africa has been related to compaction and water conservation. Controlled traffic and deep tillage resulted in higher maize yields and dry matter production, improved WUE, and improved rooting (Bennie *et al.*, 1982).

However, under higher rainfall and on more clayey soils (Berry and Mallett, 1988) obtained better, or the same yields, with no tillage compared with conventional tillage, indicating the need for site specific recommendations. In West Africa, soils are characterized by low surface porosity, poor structure, susceptibility to crust formation and low water holding capacities. Tillage incorporates organic matter, improves weed control and water conservation, and enhances root proliferation, thus increasing both fertilizer and water use efficiency.

Tillage, combined with other inputs such as fertilizer and improved cultivars, showed synergistic effects, which varied per year and cropping system. Nicou and Charreau (1985) reported an average yield increase of 22% with tillage from 38 experiments. In a millet cowpea rotation, ridging and P fertilizer input increased biomass production by 10% for millet grain, 21% for millet straw, and 27% for cowpea fodder, but reduced cowpea grain yields by 8% (Klajj *et al.*, 1994). In another experiment, tillage resulted in a 76-167% millet yield increase (Klajj and Hoogmoed, 1993). Except on sandy soils, ridging is traditionally practiced in Nigeria, Mali, Senegal, and Niger, and hilling or mounding in the Seno plain in Mali. Ridging reduces bulk density, concentrates fertility and organic matter, stimulates seedling growth and establishment, and may help reduce wind erosion (Klajj and Hoogmoed, 1993).

Where, infiltration rates are low, tied ridging leads to higher infiltration by reducing runoff. Large scale adoption of primary and secondary tillage methods may only be realized through the acceptance of mechanization. In Southern Africa, the rapid mechanization of the commercial sector from the 1930s onward has meant that almost no research on tillage using animal draught has been carried out (Morse, 1996). Still, the use of animal traction seems a practical means to increase farmers' efficiency to produce food in many production systems in SSA. Also in Southern Africa, animal traction is particularly used to cultivate steep slopes. However, farmers' application of animal traction is often limited by the availability of the traction source, fodder availability, and equipment. Within the WANA region, conventional tillage is a regular practice, *i.e.* plowing with a disc or moldboard to a depth of 20-30 cm each year, and preparing the seedbed with either a harrow or tine implement (Cooper *et al.*, 1987).

Deep tillage with moldboard in the spring of a fallow year is recommended for control of grass weeds in cereal crops. This has an additional advantage of increasing surface roughness which enhances infiltration of rainfall late in the fallow season. When followed by a shallow secondary tillage at the end of the rains, the practice leads to greater storage of soil water and increased wheat yield through soil mulch serving as an isolation layer at 8-10 cm of the soil surface (Durutan *et al.*, 1991).

However, in continuous cropping systems, this secondary tillage cannot be applied because the soil is too dry. Thus, tillage operations under continuous cropping aim mainly at seedbed preparation and depend on the implements available to cultivate the dry and hard soil. Many farmers have to delay their planting until the first rains softened the soil allowing land preparation (Pala, 1991).

In the long term, tillage can be expected to cause breakdown of the surface structure and increased crusting. In soils where the surface structure is inherently weak, cultivation rapidly leads to surface degradation, reduced infiltration, and failure of crops to emerge through the solid crusts which form, particularly toward the drier margins of the cropped area in WANA (Cooper *et al.*, 1987). If these same soils are cultivated when they are dry the lack of structure renders them very susceptible to wind erosion but its severity is not quantified.

Although systems utilizing zero tillage, reduced tillage, and/or crop residue retention treatments have been credited with reducing evaporation, as well as improving infiltration and reducing erosion in the USA (*e.g.* Papendick *et al.*, 1991) these results have proved hard to reproduce in Northern Syria (Jones, 1997). Over six years of continuous barley and vetch barley rotations, any effect of zero tillage, with retention of stubble and straw, on the dry season soil water economy was negligible. The small improvements in crop performance occasionally observed may reflect a marginal reduction in evaporation in young plant stands drilled directly into the standing stubble. Pala *et al.* (2000) reported that the general trends in soil water change were the same for all tillage practices (deep moldboard, deep chisel, shallow cultivator and zero tillage) but that zero and minimum tillage treatments left more water at harvest for the

following crop compared with deep tillage practices. Furthermore, zero and minimum tillage is more energy efficient with no reductions in yield observed.

Erosion Control Measures

In SSA, common water erosion control measures comprise stone bunds, stone lines, micro-catchments (locally called *e.g.* Zai and Teras) and rows of (leguminous) trees or perennial grasses (Roose, 1989, Manu *et al.*, 1994, Van Dijk, 1997, Ouattara *et al.*, 1999). Small-scale amendments, using hand labor or simple mechanization, are often proposed for such measures. Ways to manage the soil surface to collect and /or harvest water or to counter the effects of high intensity rainfall on crust prone surfaces and so prevent runoff include crust-breaking techniques (mainly employed soon after sowing to assist crop emergence) and, more widely, various systems of ridging. These are on or slightly off the contour, often with transverse 'ties' at intervals across the furrows that restrict flow and create a pattern of infiltration basins (Dagg and Macartney, 1968, Stroosnijder and Hoogmoed, 1984, Van Der Ploeg and Reddy, 1988).

Cropping systems also play a role in reducing soil erosion. For example, in Burkina Faso, a mixed crop of sorghum and cowpea reduced runoff by 20-30% compared to sorghum alone, and by 5-10% compared to cowpea alone, resulting in a reduction in soil erosion of 80 and 45-55%, respectively (Zougmore *et al.*, 1998). In South Africa (Haylett, 1960) found soil loss to be 44 times higher under continuous maize cropping compared with natural vegetation.

In addition, the strips between fields have positive effects on soil and water conservation, reduce soil erosion, and may contribute to the farmers income (*e.g.* through selling of woven products, fodder for animals, traditional medicine etc.). Examples are strips of *Vetiver* grass (*Vetiveria zizanioides* and *V. nigriflora*) found in Burkina Faso, Kenya, Mali, Nigeria, Tanzania, Tunisia, and Zimbabwe (Vietmeyer and Ruskin, 1993) or *Andropogon spp.* or *Panicum maximum*. Hedgerows of shrubs or small trees are also being planted as observed in Kenya (Kiepe, 1995) and Senegal (Perez *et al.*, 1998). Similar systems are currently being tested in WANA for instance in Egypt (Anonymous, 1999a) Morocco (Boutfirass *et al.*,

1999) and Syria (Somi and Abdul Aal, 1999). Larger scale alternatives include contour strips (Carter *et al.*, 1988) and various bunding and terracing systems as part of an integrated soil and land management approach. Terracing may possibly be more appropriate in the wetter environments where soil and water conservation efforts focus more on prevention of massive soil erosion, as e.g. in the hilly areas of northern Syria, where olive plantations have substantially expanded recently (Anonymous, 1999b). Evaporative losses from crops, weeds, and soil surface are partly a function of wind speed and, in dry conditions, appreciable savings of water may be achieved by reducing the wind flow through a crop.

In Niger, windbreaks of neem trees increased millet yields by approximately 20% (Long and Persaud, 1988), while in Nigeria, Eucalyptus trees increased yields by 50% (Onyewotu *et al.*, 1998). In addition, windbreaks may have another beneficial effect through control of wind erosion. Nevertheless, windbreaks are rarely part of indigenous systems. If small farmers are to adopt them, they must be seen to have intrinsic economic value additional to any conservation role, as is the case for fodder shrubs and trees (*Acacia* and *Atriplex* spp) in WANA (Jones and Harris, 1993, Lamers *et al.*, 1994, Anonymous, 1999a).

Cropping System Management

During the last decades, attention has been paid to the design of more productive and stable systems through improved cropping system management. This comprises various aspects, such as the use of appropriate crop varieties, improved cropping patterns, relay-cropping, and cultural techniques. The suggested technology packages vary with agro-ecological conditions and farmers objectives.

Crop Varieties

The identification of appropriate crops and cultivars with optimum physiology, morphology and phenology to suit local environmental conditions, especially the pattern of water availability, is one of the important research areas within cropping systems management for improved WUE. Short duration varieties for SSA that mitigate the effects of drought periods (often occurring at the beginning

and end of the growing season) are urgently needed and being developed. Such cultivars (preferably also with higher harvest indices) are considered a key component of management strategies in the drought prone areas. However, many of the currently available cultivars are susceptible to insect pests and bird damage (*i.e.* picking of grains because other feed cannot be found yet) and are more demanding in terms of soil and management conditions. In the WANA region, the varieties should be tolerant to cold drought and heat resistant to diseases and insects have vigorous early growth and are of good quality and high yielding. Early and complete canopy establishment to shade the soil and reduce evaporative loss from the soil surface can significantly improve the WUE of winter rainfall crops in this region and also, apparently of summer rainfall crops over much of the semi arid tropics (Gregory, 1991). For instance, Cham 1 an improved durum wheat variety provided 3 to 86% grain yield increase compared to Hourani, a local durum cultivar, under different water and nitrogen regimes in three distinct seasons (Pala *et al.*, 1996a). These results also show that improved cultivars may not render increased yields unless cultural practices are applied in an appropriate and timely manner.

Intercropping

Greater efficiency of resource utilization is expected from intercropping and mixed cropping in a wide range of environments (Willey, 1979 and Francis, 1989). However, these generalizations do not necessarily hold true in the more extreme environments. If rainfall is infrequent, evaporative losses from the usually dry soil surface may be relatively unimportant and if water rather than radiation is limiting, intercrops grown under a cereal canopy (supposed to utilize low intensity radiation that would otherwise be 'wasted') may in fact compete heavily with the cereal for the limited water available.

This has been demonstrated in Botswana, where intercropped cowpea had the same effect as weeds in dry years even at very low plant density cowpea was able to devastate the adjacent rows of sorghum (Rees, 1986a). In wet years, small grain yield advantages from intercropping could be recorded, but over a run of years, intercropping greatly increased yield variation and the risk of total crop failure (Jones, 1987).

Such results, however, although under different bio-physical conditions, contrast strongly with results from West Africa. Subsistence farmers practice forms of intercropping (e.g. millet with cowpea, sorghum, maize, or groundnut) that exhibit high complementarities between component crops and reduce the risk of crop failure (Swinton and Dueson, 1988) and these traditional production systems have a total yield advantage and are more stable than sole cropping (Fussell and Serafini, 1987, Shetty *et al.*, 1987). An additional benefit was the reduced Striga infestation in millet/groundnut systems (N'tare *et al.*, 1989). Replacement of cowpea by *Stylosanthes hamata* resulted in a higher WUE (Garba and Renard, 1991).

Relay Cropping

Relay cropping, the practice of growing a short-duration, fast-growing secondary crop usually a legume after the principal cereal crop is a well-known strategy. In the southern Sahel favorable rainfall years do occur and these must be fully exploited, ensuring use of any stored soil water. The need for such a strategy is greatest on sandy soils with low water-holding capacities and subject to high rates of evaporative loss. It is, however, difficult to predict whether or not the coming rainy season is likely to be favorable. Hence, recent efforts have been made to predict the essential characteristics of the approaching rainy season and tailor crop management decisions to them (e.g., Sivakumar, 1988, 1993). Although the economic feasibility of relay cropping systems is still to be determined in the Sahel, in semi arid Zimbabwe relay cropping of maize and sunflower proved profitable (Nyakatawa and Nyati, 1998).

Cultural Techniques

Timely cultural techniques, such as sowing with the first substantial rains early weeding and thinning are important for increased use of soil water and consequently good yields. They also have synergistic effects with improved soil management practices, improved cultivars and higher crop density (Fussell *et al.*, 1987). In the intercrop production system adjusting cowpea sowing time to the millet's growth cycle and the probable length of the rainy season is a technique that might increase cowpea yields (N'tare *et al.*, 1989).

In WANA any husbandry technique that facilitates rapid canopy development and enables the crop to cover the soil surface, to shade out weeds, and also to reduce wind speed through the crop may, in most circumstances, be expected to increase crop competitiveness and WUE (Cooper and Gregory, 1987). Practices that particularly contribute to this are early sowing, selection of varieties with rapid early growth (under cool conditions) adequate fertilization and adequate plant population and close spacing (Gregory, 1991).

Sowing Date

Within the concept of improved WUE water transpired by crops should be increased relative to evaporation from the soil surface. Since, transpiration efficiency is a function of the atmospheric saturation deficit, *i.e.* relative dryness of the air directing biomass production into periods of lowest atmospheric demand confers an advantage (Acevedo *et al.*, 1991, Gupta, 1995). This so-called "seasonal shifting" can improve the water use efficiency of crops to a great extent and allow for better use of limited (rain) water and /or large water savings in crop production (Seckler, 1996). Timely sowing on the basis of a scientific method rather than a traditional method increased millet yields in Nigeria by 20-40% (Onyewotu *et al.*, 1998).

In WANA, despite temperature limitations to growth, it pays to sow early (late fall, early winter) so that as much as possible of the crops growth cycle is completed within the cool rainy winter/early spring period (Cooper and Gregory, 1987) while the earliness depends on the tillage/ crop rotation system employed (Pala, 1991). Stapper and Harris (1989) simulated on the basis of field experiments that for northern Syria, each one week delay in sowing after November 1st will reduce wheat yields by 4.2%. In the same region (Acevedo *et al.*, 1991) observed a yield decrease of 9 and 22 kg ha⁻¹ day⁻¹ in areas with 280 and 330 mm long term average rainfall, respectively, if planting was delayed from late October to late January. Overall yield loss was about 50% in both areas.

Mean rainfall use efficiency of barley decreased from 12 kg ha⁻¹ mm⁻¹ at early planting to about 6 kg ha⁻¹ mm⁻¹ at late planting. Similar considerations lie behind the attempts to persuade farmers to move from spring to winter sowing of chickpea. Yield increases of 30-70% have been

reported for winter-sown chickpea compared to spring-sown chickpea (Keatinge and Cooper, 1984, Pala and Mazid, 1992a) resulting in increased WUE by 78% (Brown *et al.*, 1989) and more than 100% (Keatinge and Cooper, 1983). Likewise, early sowing of lentil in mid November increased seed yield by 20-25% compared with late sowing in early January (Silim *et al.*, 1991, Pala and Mazid, 1992b).

Crop Density Improvement

Economic crop yields arise from plant densities that minimize inter and intra row competition, which widely depends on environmental conditions, while cereal grain yield is the product of heads per unit area, kernels per head, and kernel weight. The seeding density, plant distribution and genotype in a given region have substantial effects on these components. Increasing the seeding density can increase the heads per unit area but may reduce the other two components (Joseph *et al.*, 1985). Among yield components there is compensation which tends to minimize yield loss when one component is reduced, but such compensation may not be complete.

In the case of legumes, the optimum plant density depends upon environmental conditions and the genotype. A sowing density of 300-450 germinable lentil seed per m² generally resulted in the highest yield under Syrian conditions (Silim *et al.*, 1990). The effect of increased seeding density was more apparent at the earliest sowing date, which also resulted in a higher yield, decreasing when the sowing date was delayed. Tall and erect chickpea varieties respond better to increased plant population than the spreading types (Singh, 1981, Keatinge and Cooper, 1984). The yields of these genotypes at a density of 50 plants m⁻² are increased significantly compared to 33 plants m⁻² though the lower plant density appears to be optimum for a wide range of environments (Saxena, 1981). N'tare *et al.* (1989) concluded from their millet/cowpea intercrop experiments that millet yields were not greatly reduced by increasing cowpea densities when soil water and fertility were adequate.

Bationo *et al.* (1990) observed that low plant density in farmers' fields is the primary reason for low crop response to applied fertilizer. Manu *et al.*, (1994) demonstrated on farm the yield increasing effect of increased millet population under adequate nutrition. In addition low plant densities can give

rise to below optimal crop WUE because the ratio of soil evaporation to crop transpiration may be increased. Wallace *et al.* (1988) working on sparse millet crops in Niger, estimated that about 36% of the seasonal rainfall of 562 mm could be lost as direct evaporation from the surface. Higher plant densities, therefore, increase WUE and yield (Gandah, 1988).

However, while the densest populations of sorghum in Botswana produced the most dry matter (per unit area and per mm of rain) they used up the available soil water sooner between the infrequent rainstorms. Thus, they became stressed earlier than did sparser crops such that flowering was often delayed or failed completely (Rees, 1986b, Jones, 1987). Even where flowering occurred intense competition in the denser populations kept individual plants very small, and with decreasing size the transfer of dry matter into the grain became rapidly less efficient. The greatest WUE of sorghum grain production was achieved by the sparser populations which left much of the soil surface exposed to solar radiation.

This finding is also applied by commercial farmers in the dry parts of South Africa growing their maize in rows 2-3 m apart. Van Averbek and Marais (1992) found that the maize plant population for optimum yield decreased from 60000 plants ha⁻¹ with 650 mm water supply to 10000 plants ha⁻¹ when 240 mm water is available. Similarly, olive growers in the dry areas of WANA plant trees at very wide spacing such that the canopy cover remains mostly below 25%. Frequent tillage between the trees controls weeds and also conserves soil water through a 'dry mulch' effect.

Soil Fertility Management

Given the inherent low fertility of many dry area soils judicious use of farmyard manure and inorganic fertilizer is particularly important. Extensive work in Niger (e.g. Onken *et al.*, 1988, Payne *et al.*, 1991, Klaij and Vachaud, 1992) Syria (e.g. Cooper *et al.*, 1987, Pala *et al.*, 1996b, Ryan, 1997) Turkey (Kalayci *et al.*, 1991) and Tunisia (Mechergui *et al.*, 1991) has demonstrated the benefits of appropriate fertilization on WUE and therefore on production and yield stability of millet in SSA and of winter-sown crops, especially wheat and barley, in WANA. All farmers in semi-arid environments face limits to crop and animal

productivity. Yet, the use of fertilizer, hired labor and other inputs can still make a difference for farmers wealthy enough to secure such inputs. For example, it has been found in the marginal regions of Burkina Faso and Ethiopia that the average grain yield from the wealthier farmers can be twice that of the poorer farmers cultivating adjacent fields in the same communities (Webb and Reardon, 1992).

Weed Control

Weeds compete with crops for water, nutrients, and light. In dry areas, however, the main objective of weed control is to increase the water supply available to the crop. But factors such as early sowing (affecting transpiration efficiency) and mulching (reducing soil evaporation) affect both weed infestation as well as crop water availability and use (Amor, 1991). Also other management practices such as tillage, seed density, fertilizer application and crop rotations are interrelated with both weed control and water-use efficiency (Cornish and Lymberg, 1986 and Durutan *et al.*, 1991).

To minimize the competition between weeds and crops for water, it is therefore important to adopt an integrated approach to the control of weeds. Rather than relying on only one method of weed control, several possible alternatives should be used in a systematic manner, thus increasing the chance of developing economic and sustainable farming systems which are also efficient in water use (Amor, 1991). The components of integrated weed control may include, for instance, preventing weed infestation by using clean seed (to prevent weed infestation) proper and timely cultivation, crop competition, early crop development, crop rotation, grazing, hand weeding, herbicide use and biological control.

Crop Rotations

There is increasing concern about the deterioration of integrated crop/livestock systems because of the high pressure put on these systems by the ever-rising demand for food and feed. Continuous cereal systems are increasing, parallel to the increasing demand for human and animal consumption. The decline in yield under continuous cereal cropping constitutes a major problem, but the causes of the poor productivity are not yet completely clear.

Part can be explained by negative effects on physical and chemical soil properties (soil mining, organic matter content, aggregate stability etc.) and the buildup of noxious weeds, pests and pathogens, besides accumulation of allelopathic compounds (Pala *et al.*, 2000).

Including legumes in the rotation has proved to be beneficial for sustainable crop production in both regions. For instance, in southern Niger, millet cowpea or millet groundnut rotations doubled millet production over a four year period (A. Bationo, 1999, personal communication) compared with continuous millet. Similarly, it was observed that millet cowpea rotation had an effect equivalent to the addition of approximately 30 g N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ based on on-farm trials. Rotation trials in WANA demonstrated that wheat (Cham 1) yields were lowest (1000 kg ha⁻¹) under continuous cropping. Yield increases following various crops in a rotation compared with that of continuous wheat were for medic 39%, chickpea 46%, lentil 82%, vetch 84%, melon 119%, and fallow 126% (Harris, 1994).

Legumes grown in a crop sequence with cereals have a positive effect on the system's overall WUE. Because of their usually shorter growing period, some water may be left in the soil profile for the subsequent cereal crop, increasing the latter's productivity (Karaca *et al.*, 1991 and Harris, 1995). Compared with the cereal fallow system, cereal legume rotations produce yields every year, thus increasing the system's overall WUE and its output in terms of quantity as well as nutritional quality (Pala *et al.*, 1997).

Conclusions and Future Research Needs

Irrespective of the research results mentioned in this paper relating to improving water use efficiency and hence production levels, stability, and sustainability particularly under rain fed conditions, large amounts of rainwater are still lost and/or inefficiently utilized in farmers' fields. The possible mechanisms of losses and inefficiency are many, varied, and not always well quantified. Further, at different locations, it is different subsets of those mechanisms that need to be understood and remedied within the local human and socio-economic context if actual production per unit area is to reach the agricultural production potential in the dry areas of WANA and SSA. Biophysically, solutions too many of the problems will require the

improvement of soil, water and crop management at the field, plot and farm level: first, to increase the capture and retention of incoming (rain) water and second to maximize the proportion of that water productively transpired by the crop.

The choice of crops for the production systems, cultivar, sowing date, plant density, fertilizer management and control of diseases, insects and weeds needs to best suit the local environmental conditions. Given the low and erratic precipitation for crop production in the dry areas, further research should focus on improving water use efficiency associated with increased production per unit area, and improved production stability. Adaptive research and a farmer participatory approach, building on past experience are key issues for identification of acceptable techniques that match local needs and available resources if potential yield levels obtained in on station research are to be achieved in farmer's fields. The established collaboration and exchange of information between agricultural scientists and close linkages between scientists, extension workers, and farmers within the OSWU consortium will allow a more rapid and sustainable solution to the food production problems and inefficient use of limited water resources.

There is also an integrated approach being tested to simultaneously optimize soil water and nutrient use by crops in dry areas for greater efficiency and sustainability as for too long have these two aspects been researched independently. The decision support tool indicated also the need for considering downstream effects. An integrated catchment management approach where soil water and nutrient balances are determined as per the land use pattern is therefore considered to be investigated within the consortium research agenda but awaits further funding for execution.

In the future, investigations on optimizing the use of water for a cropping system should focus not only at the level of a single field, but rather at the level of a watershed. Crop simulation modeling linked to GIS to capture spatial variability can facilitate the development of recommendations for possible techniques or strategies for farmers in a specific biophysical environment and allow identification of eventual positive or negative off site effects. Further, including these biophysical strategies in a bio-economic model is considered a valuable approach to match the identified strategies with the socio-economic conditions of resource poor

farmers in the semi arid regions of WANA and SSA, and to identify the best bet options that the farmers can test. It is recommended that careful attention should be paid to the definition of WUE, with regard to inputs and outputs and the time and spatial scales at which it is being estimated in order to facilitate comparison between different studies. Whenever possible the term WUE should be replaced with more specific definitions and the calculation procedures should be clearly explained.

The focus for further research on optimizing soil water use in the dry areas will have to be on impact assessment of research efforts so far and the identification of the reasons behind the still existing gap between known principles and the situation in the farmers fields. Further recommendations need to be developed in a more site- and situation specific way considering not only the farmers bio-physical but also his socio-economic environment. Modeling techniques in combination with GIS may facilitate the development of management options, which are better, tailored to a specific farmer's conditions and, therefore, have a better chance of being adopted.

References

- Acevedo, E., H. C. Harris and P. J. M. Cooper, (1991) Crop architecture and water use efficiency in Mediterranean environments. In: H.C. Harris, P. J. M. Cooper and M. Pala (Eds.), Soil and crop management for improved water use efficiency in rainfed areas, ICARDA, Aleppo, pp: 106-118.
- Amor, R. L. (1991) Effect of weeds on water use of rainfed crops, In: H. C. Harris, P. J. M. Cooper and M. Pala (Eds.), Soil and crop management for improved water use efficiency in rainfed areas, ICARDA, Aleppo, pp: 199-203.
- Anonymous (1999a) Mandate and Sustainability of Matrouh Adaptive Research Center, Matrouh Resource Management Project, World Bank IDA Credit No. 2504-EGT, World Bank, Washington, pp: 23.
- Anonymous (1999b) Protecting hillsides Farmer participatory research in the olive zone of northwestern Syria, Land Management Project, ICARDA, Aleppo, pp: 4.
- Bationo, A., S. H. Chien, J. Henao, C. E. Christianson and A. U. Mkwunye (1990)

- Agronomic evaluation of two unacidulated and partially acidulated phosphate rocks indigenous to Niger, *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, **54**: 1772-1777.
- Bationo, A., B. J. Ndunguru, B. R. Ntare, C. B. Christianson and A. U. Mokwunye (1991) Fertilizer management strategies for legume based cropping systems in the West African semi arid tropics, In: C. Johansen, K. K. Lee and K. L. Sahrawat (Eds.), Phosphorus nutrition of grain legumes in the semi arid tropics, ICRISAT, Patancheru, pp: 213-226.
- Bennie, A. T. P., F. T. P. Botha and A. F. Ferreira, (1982) The effects of different deep tillage methods on maize growth, *Crop Production*, **11**: 74-78.
- Berry, W. A. J. and J. B. Mallett (1988) The effect of the tillage: maize residue interactions upon soil water storage, *South African Journal of Plant and Soil*, **5**: 57-64.
- Beukes, D. J., A. T. P. Bennie and M. Hensley (1999) Optimizing of soil water use in the dry crop areas of South Africa, In: N. Van Duivenbooden, M. Pala, C. Studer and C. L. Biolders (Eds.), Efficient soil water use: the key to sustainable crop production in the dry areas of West Asia, and North and Sub-Saharan Africa, ICARDA, Aleppo/ICRISAT, Patancheru, pp: 165-191.
- Boutfirass, M., M. El Gharous, M. El Mourid and M. Karrou (1999) Optimizing soil water use research in deficient water environments of Morocco, In: N. Van Duivenbooden, M. Pala, C. Studer and C. L. Biolders (Eds.), Efficient soil water use: the key to sustainable crop production in the dry areas of West Asia and North and Sub Saharan Africa, ICARDA, Aleppo/ ICRISAT, Patancheru, pp: 125-142.
- Brown, S. C., P. J. Gregory, P. J. M. Cooper and J. D. H. Keatinge (1989) Root and shoot growth and water use of chickpea (*Cicer arietinum*) grown in dryland conditions: effects of sowing date and genotype, *Journal of Agricultural Science*, Cambridge, **113**: 41-49.
- Campbell, R. B., R. E. Sojka and D. L. Karlen (1984) Conservation tillage for soybean in the U.S southeastern coastal plain, *Soil and Tillage Research*, **4**: 531-541.
- Carter, C., J. Siebert, E. Modiakgotla, G. Heinrich and S. Masikara (1988) Rainfall runoff management in Botswana, In: P. W. Unger, T. V. Sneed, W. J. Jordan and R. Jensen (Eds.), Challenges in dryland agriculture: A global perspective, Texas Agricultural Experiment Station, Amarillo/ Bushland, pp: 239-241.
- Cooper, P. J. M. and P. J. Gregory (1987) Soil water management in the rainfed farming systems of the Mediterranean region, *Soil Use and Management*, **3**: 57-62.
- Cooper, P. J. M., P. J. Gregory, D. Tully and H. C. Harris (1987) Improving water use efficiency of annual crops in the rainfed farming systems of West Asia and North Africa, *Experimental Agriculture*, **23**: 113-158.
- Cornish, P. S. and J. R. Lymberg (1986) Effects of stubble retention and weed growth on water conservation over summer, In: J. E. Pratley and P. S. Cornish (Eds.), Proceedings of conference on recent advances in weed and crop residue management, Southern Conservation Farming Group Occasional Publication No. 2, WaggaWagga, pp: 39-40.
- Dagg, M. and J. C. Macartney (1968) The agronomic efficiency of the NIAAE tied ridge system of cultivation, *Experimental Agriculture*, **4**: 279-294.
- Durutan, N., M. Guler, M. Karaca, K. Meyveci, A. Avcin and H. Eyuboglu (1991) Effect of various components of the management package on weed control in dryland agriculture, In: H. C. Harris, P. J. M. Cooper and M. Pala (Eds.), Soil and crop management for improved water use efficiency in rainfed areas, ICARDA, Aleppo, Syria, pp: 220-234.
- Francis, C. A. (1989) Biological efficiencies in multiple cropping systems, *Advances in Agronomy*, pp: 42.
- Fussell, L. K. and P. G. Serafini (1987) Intercropping: its future as a cropping system in the drought prone tropics of West Africa, In: J. M. Menyonga T. Bezuneh and A. Youdeowei (Eds.), Food grain production in semi arid Africa, OAU/STR-SAFGRAD, Ouagadougou, pp: 559-565.

- Fussell, L. K., P. G. Serafini, A. Bationo and M. C. Klaij (1987) Management practices to increase yield and yield stability of millet in Africa, In: Proceedings of the International Pearl Millet Workshop, 7-11 April 1986, ICRISAT, Patancheru, pp: 255-268.
- Gandah, M. (1988) Response of Pearl Millet [*Pennisetum americanum* L. (Schum)] to soil moisture in one agro climatological Zone of Niger, West Africa, M. Sc. thesis, Texas A. and M. Univ., College Station, pp: 113.
- Garba, M. and C. Renard (1991) Biomass production, yields and water use efficiency in some pearl millet/ legume cropping systems at Sadore, Niger, In: M. V. K. Sivakumar, J. S. Wallace, C. Renard and C. Giroux (Eds.), Soil and water balance in the Sudano-Sahelian zone, IAHS Press, Institute of Hydrology, Wallingford, pp: 431-439.
- Gregory, P. J. (1991) Concepts of water use efficiency, In: H. C. Harris, P. J. M. Cooper and M. Pala (Eds.), Soil and crop management for improved water use efficiency in rainfed areas, ICARDA, Aleppo, pp: 9-20.
- Gupta, U. S. (1995) Role of humidity in dryland crop production In: U. S. Gupta (Ed.), Production and improvement of crops for drylands, Science Publishers Inc., New Delhi, pp: 271-295.
- Harris, H. C., A. E. Osman, P. J. M. Cooper and M. J. Jones (1991) The management of crop rotations for greater water use efficiency under rainfed conditions, In: H. C. Harris, P. J. M. Cooper and M. Pala (Eds.), Soil and crop management for improved water use efficiency in rainfed areas, ICARDA, Aleppo, pp: 237-250.
- Harris, H. C. (1994) Water use efficiency of crop rotations in a Mediterranean environment, *Aspects of Applied Biology*, **38**: 165-172.
- Harris, H. C. (1995) Long term trials on soil and crop management at ICARDA, *Advances in Soil Science*, **19**: 447-469.
- Haylett, D. G. (1960) Run-off and soil erosion studies at Pretoria, *South African Journal of Agricultural Science*, **3**: 379-394.
- Jones, M. J. (1987) Soil water and crop production in Botswana, *Soil Use and Management*, **3**: 74-79.
- Jones, M. J. (1997) Tillage and barley residue management trial at Breda, In: 1995 Annual Report for Farm Resource Management Program, ICARDA, Aleppo, pp: 64-72.
- Jones, M. J. and H. C. Harris (1993) The Atriplex hedge trial at Ghrerife, In: 1992 Annual Report for Farm Resource Management Program, ICARDA, Aleppo, pp: 68-73.
- Joseph, K. D. S. M., M. M. Alley, D. E. Braun and W. D. Gravelle (1985) Row spacing and seeding rate effects on yield and yield components of soft red winter wheat, *Agronomy Journal*, **77**: 211-214.
- Kalayci, M., S. Siirt, M. Aydin and U. Ozkan (1991) The effect of N fertilizer on winter wheat in the western transitional zone of Turkey, In: H. C. Harris, P. J. M. Cooper and M. Pala (Eds.), Soil and crop management for improved water use efficiency in rainfed areas, ICARDA, Aleppo, pp: 168-176.
- Keatinge, J. D. H. and P. J. M. Cooper (1983) Kabuli chickpea as a winter sown crop in northern Syria: Moisture relations and crop productivity, *Journal of Agricultural Science, Cambridge*, **100**: 667-680.
- Keatinge, J. D. H. and P. J. M. Cooper (1984) Physiological and Moisture-use studies on growth and development of winter-sown chickpeas, In: K. B. Singh and M. C. Saxena (Eds.), Ascochyta blight and winter sowing of Chickpeas, Martinus Nijhoff/ Dr. W. Junk Publishers, The Hague, pp: 141-157.
- Kiepe, P. (1995) No Runoff, no soil loss: soil and water conservation in hedgerow barrier systems. PhD Thesis, *Wageningen Agricultural University*, Wageningen, pp: 156.
- Klaij, M. C. and W. B. Hoogmoed (1993) Soil management for crop production in the West African Sahel, II, Emergence, establishment and yield of pearl millet, *Soil and Tillage Research*, **25**: 301-315.
- Klaij, M. C. and G. Vachaud (1992) Seasonal water balance of a sandy soil in Niger cropped with pearl millet, based on profile moisture

- measurements, *Agricultural Water Management*, **21**: 313-330.
- Klajj, M. C., C. Renard and K. C. Reddy (1994) Low input technology options for millet based cropping systems in the Sahel, *Experimental Agriculture*, **30**: 77-82.
- Lal, R. (1976) No-tillage effects on soil properties under different crops in Western Nigeria, *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, **40**: 762-768.
- Lamers, J. P. A., K. Michels and R. J. Vandenbeldt (1994) Trees and windbreaks in the Sahel: establishment, growth, nutritive, and calorific values, *Agroforestry Systems*, **26**: 171-184.
- Long, S. P. and N. Persaud (1988) Influence of neem (*Azadiracta indica*) windbreaks on millet yield, microclimate and water use in Niger, West Africa, In: P.W. Unger, T.V. Sneed, W.J. Jordan and R. Jensen (Eds.), *Challenges in dryland agriculture: A global perspective*, Texas Agricultural Experiment Station, Amarillo/ Bushland, pp: 313-314.
- Manu, A., T. L. Thurow, A. S. R. Juo, I. Sanguina, M. Gandah and I. Mahamane (1994) Sustainable land management in the Sahel: a case study of an agricultural watershed at Hamdallaye, Niger, Trop Soils/TAMU Bulletin 94-01, Trop Soil, Texas A and M Univ., pp: 44.
- Mechergui, M., A. Gharbi and S. Lazaar (1991) The impact of N and P fertilizers on root growth, total yield and water use efficiency of rainfed cereals in Tunisia, In: H. C. Harris, P. J. M. Cooper and M. Pala (Eds.), *Soil and crop management for improved water use efficiency in rainfed areas*, ICARDA, Aleppo, pp: 153-158.
- Morse, K. (1996) A review of soil and water management research in semi-arid areas of southern and eastern Africa. Natural Resources Institute, Chatham, pp: 187.
- Muehlbauer, F. J. and W. J. Keiser (Eds.) (1994) Expanding the production and use of cool season food legumes, A global perspective of persistent constraints and of opportunities and strategies for further increasing the productivity and use of Pea, Lentil, Faba Bean, Chickpea, and Grasspea in different farming systems, *Kluwer Academic Publishers*, London, pp: 991.
- Nicou, R. and C. Charreau (1985) Travail du sol et économie de l'eau en Afrique de l'Ouest, In: H. W. Ohm, and J. G. Naggy (Eds.), *Technologie Appropriée pour les paysans des zones semi-arides de l'Afrique de l'Ouest*, Perdue University, West Lafayette, pp: 9-37.
- N'tare, B. R., P. G. Serafini and L. K. Fussell (1989) Recent developments in millet/cowpea cropping systems for low rainfall areas of the Sudano- Sahelian zone of West Africa, In: Soil, crop and water management systems for rainfed agriculture in the Sudano-Sahelian Zone, ICRISAT, Patancheru, pp: 277-290.
- Nyakatawa, E. Z. and C. T. Nyati (1998) Yields of maize and sunflower in relation to sowing time and rainfall distribution under three cropping systems in a semi-arid region in Zimbabwe, *Tropical Agriculture (Trinidad)* **75**: 428-433.
- Onken, A. B., C. W. Wendt and A. D. Halvorson (1988) Soil fertility and water use efficiency, In: P. W. Unger, T. V. Sneed, W. J. Jordan and R. Jensen (Eds.), *Challenges in dryland agriculture : A global perspective*. Texas Agricultural Experiment Station, Amarillo/Bushland, Texas, USA, pp. 441-44.
- Onyewotu, L. O. Z., C. J. Stigter, E. O. Oladipos and J. J. Owanubi (1998) Yields of millet between shelter belts in semi-arid northern Nigeria, with a traditional and a scientific method of determining sowing date, and at two levels of organic manuring, *Netherlands Journal of Agricultural Science*, **46**: 53-64.
- Osman, A. E., M. H. Ibrahim and M. A. Jones (Eds) (1990) The role of legumes in the farming systems of the Mediterranean areas, *Developments in Plant and Soil Sciences*, 38, Kluwer Academic Publisher, Dordrecht, pp: 310.
- Ouattara, B., V. Hien and F. Lompo (1999) Development of water management technologies for rainfed crops in Burkina Faso., In: N. Van Duivenbooden, M. Pala, C. Studer and C. L. Biolders (Eds.), *Efficient soil water use: the key to sustainable crop production in the dry areas of West*

- Asia, and North and Sub-Saharan Africa, ICARDA, Aleppo/ ICRISAT, Patancheru, pp: 265-281.
- Pala, M. (1991) The effect of crop management on increased production through improved water use efficiency at sowing, In: H. C. Harris, P. J. M. Cooper and M. Pala (Eds.), Soil and crop management for improved water use efficiency in rainfed areas, ICARDA, Aleppo, pp: 87-105.
- Pala, M. and A. Mazid (1992a) On farm assessment of improved crop production practices in Northwest Syria, I. Chickpea, *Experimental Agriculture*, **28**: 175-184.
- Pala, M. and A. Mazid (1992b) On farm assessment of improved crop production practices in Northwest Syria, II. Lentil, *Experimental Agriculture*, **28**: 185-193.
- Pala, M., C. S. Stockle, and H. C. Harris (1996a) Simulation of durum wheat (*Triticum turgidum* ssp. Durum) growth under different water and nitrogen regimes in a Mediterranean environment using, *Crop Syst. Agricultural Systems*, **51**: 147-163.
- Pala, M., A. Matar and A. Mazid (1996b) Assessment of the effects of environmental factors on the response of wheat to fertilizer in on farm trials in a mediterranean type environment, *Experimental Agriculture*, **32**: 339-349.
- Pala, M., H. C. Harris, J. Ryan, R. Makboul and S. Dozom (2000) Tillage Systems and stubble management in a Mediterranean type environment in relation to crop yield and soil moisture, *Experimental Agriculture*, **36**: 223-242.
- Pala, M., E. Armstrong and C. Johansen (2000) The role of legumes in sustainable cereal production in rainfed areas, In: R. Knight (Ed.), Linking research and marketing opportunities for pulses in the 21st century, *Current Plant Science and Biotechnology in Agriculture*, **34**, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, pp: 323-334.
- Papendick, R. I., J. F. Parr and R. E. Meyer (1991) Tillage and stubble management: ongoing research in USA. In: H. C. Harris, P. J. M. Cooper and M. Pala (Eds.), Soil and crop management for improved water use efficiency in rainfed areas, ICARDA, Aleppo, pp: 66-78.
- Payne, W. A., R. J. Lascano, L. R. Hossner, C. W. Wendt and A. B. Onken (1991) Pearl millet growth as influenced by phosphorus and water, *Agronomy Journal*, **83**: 942-948.
- Perez, P., J. Albergel, M. Diatta, M. Grouzis and M. Sene (1998) Rehabilitation of a semi-arid ecosystem in Senegal, 2, Farm plot experiments, *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, **70**: 19-29.
- Rees, D. J. (1986a) Crop growth, development and yield in semi-arid conditions in Botswana, II, The effects of intercropping Sorghum bicolor with *Vigna unguiculata*, *Experimental Agriculture*, **22**: 169-177.
- Rees, D. J. (1986b) Crop growth, development and yield in semi-arid conditions in Botswana, I, The effects of population density and row spacing on Sorghum bicolor, *Experimental Agriculture*, **22**: 153-167.
- Roose, E. (1989) Gestion conservatoire des eaux et de la fertilité des sols dans les paysagessoudano-sahéliens de l'Afrique Occidentale, In: Soil, crop, and water management systems for rainfed agriculture in the Sudano-Sahelian Zone, ICARISAT, Patancheru, pp: 55-72.
- Ryan, J. (Ed.) (1997) Accomplishments and future challenges in dryland soil fertility research in the Mediterranean area, ICARDA, Aleppo, pp: 369.
- Saxena, M. C. (1981) Agronomy of Lentils, In: C. Webb and G. C. Hawtin (Eds.), Lentils, CAB International, Wallingford, pp: 119-129.
- Seckler, D. (1996) The new era of water resources management: from "dry" to "wet" water sowings, Research Report 1, International Water Management Institute, Colombo, Sri Lanka, pp: 23.
- Shetty, S. V. R., B. Kuita, A. Coulibaly and I. Kassembara (1987) Cultures associées au Mali, Progrès de la recherche agronomique, In: Les Cultures Associées au Mali, ICARISAT/IER, Bamako, pp: 31-51.
- Silim, S. N., M. C. Saxena and W. Erskine (1990) Seeding density and row spacing for lentil in rainfed Mediterranean environments, *Agronomy Journal*, **82**: 927-930.

- Silim, S. N., M. C. Saxena and W. Erskine (1991) Effect of sowing date on the growth and yield of lentil in a rainfed Mediterranean environment, *Experimental Agriculture*, **27**: 145-154.
- Singh, K. B. (1981) Yield potential of tall chickpeas at increased plant density, *International Chickpea Newsletter*, **4**: 10-11.
- Sivakumar, M. V. K. (1988) Predicting rainy season potential from the onset of rains in the Sahelian and Sudanian climatic zones of West Africa, *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, **42**: 295-305.
- Sivakumar, M. V. K. (1993) Growth and yield of millet and cowpea in relay and intercrop systems in the Sahelian zone in years when the onset of the rainy season is early, *Experimental Agriculture*, **29**: 417-427.
- Somi, G. and A. Abdul Aal (1999) Surface water resources management using runoff harvesting and spreading techniques in the Syria steppe (1995-1998 seasons), Syrian Ministry of Agriculture and Agrarian Reform, Department of Water Management/IDRC/UNDP, Damascus, pp: 34.
- Stapper, M. and H. C. Harris (1989) Assessing the productivity of wheat genotypes in a Mediterranean climate, using a crop simulation model, *Field Crops Research*, **20**: 129-152.
- Stroosnijder, L. and W. B. Hoogmoed (1984) Crust formation on sandy soils in the Sahel, II, Tillage and its effect on the water balance, *Soil and Tillage Research*, **4**: 321-337.
- Swinton, S. M. and R. R. Dueson (1988) The rationality of intercropping in Sahelian Africa: evidence from Niger. In: P.W. Unger, T.V. Sneed, W.J. Jordan & R. Jensen (Eds.), Challenges in dryland agriculture: A global perspective, Texas Agricultural Experiment Station, Amarillo/ Bushland, pp: 601-603.
- Van Averbek, W. and J. N. Marais (1992) Maize response to plant population and soil water supply: 1, Yield of grain and total above ground biomass, *South African Journal of Plant and Soil*, **9**: 186-192.
- Van der Ploeg, J. and K. C. Reddy (1988) Water conservation techniques for sorghum growing areas of Niger, In: P. W. Unger, T. V. Sneed, W. J. Jordan and R. Jensen (Eds.), Challenges in dryland agriculture: A global perspective, Texas Agricultural Experiment Station, Amarillo/ Bushland, pp: 157-159.
- Van Dijk, J. A. (1997) Indigenous soil and water conservation by Teras in eastern Sudan, *Land Degradation and Development*, **8**: 17-26.
- Vietmeyer, N. D. and F. R. Ruskin (Eds.) (1993) Vetiver Grass: A thin green line against erosion, National Academy Press, Washington D.C., USA, pp: 157.
- Wallace, J. S., J. H. C. Gash, D. D. McNeil and M. V. K. Sivakumar (1988) Evaporation from a sparse dryland millet crop in Niger, West Africa, In: P. W. Unger, T. V. Sneed, W. J. Jordan and R. Jensen (Eds.), Challenges in dryland agriculture: A global perspective, Texas Agricultural Experiment Station, Amarillo/ Bushland, pp: 325-327.
- Webb, P. and T. Reardon (1992) Drought impact and household response in East and West Africa, *Quarterly Journal of International Agriculture*, **3**: 221-259.
- Willey, R. (1979) Intercropping its importance and research needs, Part 1, Competition and yield advantages, *Field Crop, Abstracts*, **32**: 1-10.
- Wiltshire, G. H. and C. C. du Preez (1993) Long term effects of conservation practices on the nitrogen fertility of the soil cropped annually to wheat, *South African Journal of Plant and Soil*, **10**: 70-75.
- Zougmore, R., F. Kamboun, K. Ouattara and S. Guillobez, S. (1998) The cropping system of sorghum-cowpea in the prevention of runoff and erosion in the Sahel of Burkina Faso, In: D. Buckless, A. Eteka, O. Osiname, M. Galiba and G. Galiano (Eds.), Cover crops in West Africa: contributing to sustainable agriculture, *International Development Research Centre*, Ottawa, pp: 217-224.